

A Digital Twin Architecture for Real-Time and Offline High Granularity Analysis in Smart Buildings

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Abstract

Smart buildings aim to create a safe, comfortable and sustainable environment for the occupants while increasing the energy performance of the building to reduce the environmental footprint and operational cost. Towards this direction, the use of model-based digital twins able to simulate key aspects of the building is important. Despite the utilization of various digital twin approaches for smart buildings in recent years, most of these approaches mainly focus on one aspect of the building, such as indoor environmental quality or energy consumption. This observation necessitates the development of a virtual but realistic and non-invasive environment able to simulate all the key domains of the building, including indoor air quality, thermal comfort, and energy consumption. Towards this direction, this work proposes an architecture for smart buildings investigations, that emulates the thermal comfort, air-quality, and electricity consumption of the building, while considering the activities and behavior of occupants. For simulating the building operations, ordinary differential equations and power balance modeling are incorporated to facilitate real-time or faster than real-time digital twin approaches, while computational fluid dynamics modeling is used complementarily, to enable higher granularity simulations for offline analysis. Both models have been validated in a real building achieving less than 1% average zone temperature error between the simulation models and the actual building sensor measurements. Furthermore, a user-friendly software platform has been developed and integrated with the proposed architecture, where multiple important features and characteristics have been included to enable various investigations. In particular, the developed platform enables physical and simulated building integration,

model calibration using field measurements, experimental configuration and management, execution of novel what-if investigations, and evaluation of novel algorithms using hardware-in-the-loop configurations. The proposed architecture is applied in a physical building, allowing the demonstration of several investigations and the execution of interesting use-cases.

Keywords—Digital twin, computational fluid dynamics, energy management, indoor air-quality, ordinary differential equations, sensor faults, sensor placement, smart buildings, thermal comfort.

1 Introduction

Buildings globally consume a big portion of the total electricity and account for a substantial part of Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions and therefore are playing a critical role in environmental sustainability. According to IEA (2019), the building sector represents 30% of the global energy usage and approximately 55% of the total electricity consumption. Additionally, buildings are responsible for 28% of energy-related Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) emissions worldwide (IEA, 2019). Moreover, humans spend most of their time indoors making it critical to ensure a healthy and comfortable Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)¹ (Agarwal et al., 2021). For instance, when the concentration of Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) in an indoor space exceeds the acceptable range (i.e., 0-250 parts per billion), it can cause serious short- and long-term effects can be caused to the occupants, such as, headaches, nose and throat inflammation, anxiety, and respiratory diseases. Similarly, prolonged exposure to CO₂ levels beyond the range of 400-1000 particles per million, can have as a result drowsiness, headaches, and reduced attention. On the other hand, the overall energy efficiency of a building depends on several factors, including the local generation of green energy, the electrical appliances efficiency, the thermal insulation of the building, and the operation of energy-demanding devices such as, heating and cooling systems. Therefore, building energy management systems (BEMSs) have been introduced to enhance energy efficiency, automate energy management and demand response procedures, coordinate electricity generation from distributed and Renewable Energy Sources (RES), manage indoor environmental conditions and ensure the building's sustainability (Hannah et al., 2018).

Towards the deployment of smart and sustainable buildings, technologies related to electricity generation and demand coordination, as well as IEQ management and control, must be integrated within the Internet of Things (IoT) framework (Heidari et al., 2022). In this direction, the development of digital twins and simulation models for buildings facilitate the design, performance evaluation, and solution development,

¹ IEQ accounts for Indoor Air Quality (IAQ), thermal comfort, lighting and acoustics.

as stated by Zhou et al. (2021). According to IBM (IBM, 2022), a digital twin, is a virtual model designed to accurately reflect a physical object. This virtual model (i.e., building's simulation model) should be executed in real-time or faster than real-time, while considering the representation of the key domains of a building, including electricity consumption, air quality, thermal comfort, and user behavior. Digital twins incorporate field measurements either for high-accuracy model calibration or for replicating the exact operating conditions of the building in a virtual environment. State estimation methods can further be used in the digital twin context, either for offline calibration of the model's accuracy or for online estimation of unmeasurable states that are required as inputs. The development of such digital twins enables the non-invasive evaluation of the building's performance and operation under rare or extreme conditions, which can be used for planning, management and maintenance prevention (Bosh, 2022). Additionally, the digital twin can be utilized for testing, demonstrating and evaluating novel and intelligent monitoring and control solutions in a highly realistic environment, considering Hardware-In-the-Loop (HIL) configurations, prior to their implementation in actual buildings.

Different studies have been conducted related to the development of digital twins of buildings. Khajavi et al. (2019) demonstrated how Building Information Modeling (BIM) can be combined with sensor measurements and machine learning algorithms to facilitate the development of a digital twin. In the study by Schweigkofler et al. (2022), BIM was utilized to understand the building's characteristics, such as geometry and materials. These characteristics were then combined to develop a digital twin, which was used to visualize the indoor environmental conditions in real time through an interactive dashboard. In Chen et al. (2022), an artificial intelligent approach based on a broad learning system is introduced to enhance the accuracy of a building's digital twin, with a primary focus on an industrial-level Heating, Ventilation and Air Condition (HVAC) system, including chillers, cooling towers and cooling water pumps. Such digital twins mainly focus on the thermal comfort of buildings, where the digital replica of the actual HVAC equipment can be used to optimize processes and predict failures for maintenance purposes (Hosamo et al., 2022). The aforementioned approaches provide opportunities for various investigations, including predictive maintenance and decision-making concerning the building's indoor

environment. However, they do not adequately capture the relationship between the HVAC process and the building energy performance in terms of electricity consumption and generation.

A holistic framework that simultaneously emulates all the key building domains, such as electricity consumption and generation, heating and cooling of indoor spaces, and air quality, can create new opportunities for introducing the energy sector integration approach at the building level. This approach couples all of the energy-related domains such as electricity, heating, cooling, etc. In this context, a substantial amount of electricity is required for cooling or heating a building, which impacts the operational cost, particularly in a variable electricity pricing environment. Therefore, energy management control schemes for buildings should consider electricity generation and demand, energy storage charging and discharging processes, as well as heating and cooling devices. For instance, HVAC control that considers electricity demand flexibilities (Mansy & Kwon, 2020) or a joint optimization scheme for electric vehicle charging and HVAC operation considering comfort preferences (Nguyen & Le, 2013) have been proposed, illustrating that the utilization of the energy sector integration concept can significantly reduce electricity cost. Hence, a digital twin should accurately capture the building's behavior across all critical operational sectors.

An approach for replicating the behavior of a building is to develop a digital twin by using accurate and reliable simulation models. These simulation models must accurately represent the indoor environmental conditions, capture the building's energy consumption and generation, and be capable of real time or faster than real time execution. Various approaches have been employed for this type of simulations, including mathematical optimization techniques (Ahmad et al., 2020; Ogunjuyigbe et al., 2016), heuristic optimization algorithms (Kampelis et al., 2019; Silva et al., 2019), and zone-building energy models (Naseem et al., 2022; Torrerosa et al., 2018).

An example of an optimization algorithm for modeling buildings' behavior is based on Lyapunov theory, which involves the optimal control of a dynamical system using a leveraging Lyapunov function (Shi et al., 2022). This method is commonly used for controlling queuing systems, since it does not require

information about the distribution of electric loads and does not depend on future information (Mao et al., 2016; Lin et al., 2020).

On the other hand, zone-building energy models are more specialized as they include detailed mathematical equations to describe physical phenomena (Arendt et al., 2018). These models can be utilized for several purposes, such as: the prediction of zonal states (e.g., temperature, moisture and CO₂) (Yang et al., 2015; Sang et al., 2017), contamination detection (Michaelides et al., 2014; Kyriacou et al., 2019), indoor occupancy estimation (Lam et al., 2014; Gunay et al., 2016), simulation of the performance and operation of mechanical systems such as the HVAC units (Cetin et al., 2019; Woods et al., 2019), and for the assessment of the impact of different systems on the building's energy consumption or generation (Dahanayake et al., 2017; Rhodes et al., 2015; Kamal et al., 2018). Zone-building energy models primarily rely on the fundamental heat balance principles, expressed as first-order ordinary differential equations (ODEs). The integration of the building zone dynamics with the air system, including heating, cooling, and ventilation, is achieved by solving the ODEs in order to calculate the state of various parameters such as temperature, humidity, and CO₂ of each building zone (National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 2022).

To calculate the total energy consumption of the domain of interest, the power balance approach is utilized, which involves the summation of all energy loads from the various system components at a specific timestep (National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 2022). Moreover, certain building energy simulators, like *EnergyPlus* developed by the Department of Energy of the United States of America (USA) (National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 2022), have the capability to integrate both load consumption and the energy generation from the distributed energy resources, such as generators, renewable energy resources, and energy storage units. Therefore, they are able to provide an estimation of the overall electricity power balance for the building.

Moreover, the coupling between the two approaches (ODEs and power balance) is an important aspect of zone-building energy models, as it enables the consideration of the interactions among the thermal behavior of the building, the operation of electrical appliances, the occupants' behavior, and the energy

consumption. For example, the usage of electrical appliances based on occupants' behavior can impact the heat emitted by each appliance, thereby influencing the ODE-based model's estimation of the new heat balance temperature. On the other hand, the thermal behavior of the building (e.g., temperature per zone) directly influences the operation of energy harvesting heating/cooling systems, which in turn, affects the overall energy consumption of the building. Therefore, incorporating the coupling phenomena between the thermal and power balance models can enhance the overall accuracy of the simulation. In practice, specific building simulators are designed to sequentially account for these coupling phenomena.

In general, zone-building energy models based on ordinary differential equations and power balance approach offer fast and accurate estimation of the buildings' behavior. Therefore, these models have gained significant popularity among the scientific community and have been successfully incorporated into various buildings' simulation tools, such as *EnergyPlus*. Consequently, this approach has been adopted as the primary modelling approach in the simulation layer of the proposed architecture in order to achieve an accurate and real-time (or faster than real-time) estimation of the building's operations. However, it is important to be highlighted that the accurate utilization of input data (e.g., occupant behavior, HVAC operation, etc.) and outdoor conditions is of critical importance for this modelling approach, in order to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the results. Thus, in this research study, the relevant input data have been collected from live sensor measurements or from international databases (e.g., weather files). It should also be noted that one limitation of using zone-building energy modelling approaches is the assumption of uniform indoor conditions at each zone, such as uniform temperature. As a result, these models cannot capture the details of the airflow and temperature distribution within the zone of interest (Zhang et al., 2013), while the geospatial granularity is limited to a single point per zone. This assumption is highly associated with the requirement for real-time execution, since higher granularity approaches that can achieve an increased analysis within a zone are not capable of being executed in real time.

For cases where real-time execution is not required for certain investigations, the computational fluid dynamics (CFD) modelling approach can be employed to achieve higher granularity under offline conditions. CFD models have been extensively utilized for simulating and analyzing various aspects of the indoor environment of a building, including thermal comfort (Saarinen et al., 2018), indoor air quality (Kwok et al., 2020), dust particle distribution, and chemical reactions between different contaminants (Nielsen, 2015). Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic has prompted research teams to employ CFD for the investigation of airborne pathogen droplet transmission (Sheikhnejad et al., 2022). For example, Liu et al. (2022), used CFD modelling approach to examine the impact of ventilation strategies on airborne particle exposure in a small office. In CFD modeling, the Navier-Stokes equations, which are based on the mass, energy and momentum conservation principles, are employed in combination with different turbulence models, allowing a detailed analysis of the airflow behavior and the temperature distribution profiles within each building zone.

The main drawbacks of CFD modelling are correlated with the computational time, the sensitivity and complexity of the simulations. The first drawback is associated with the fact that performing a CFD simulation is much more computationally expensive compared to simulations with ODEs-based models. This is due to the creation of a high number of multidimensional solutions for each zone based on the number of computational cells defined by the CFD grid size. However, it should be noted that even if the number of computational cells is carefully reduced to accelerate processing time, the CFD approach cannot be uniformly applied to develop real-time digital twins for buildings. Other drawbacks of the CFD modelling are the high complexity on choosing and setting-up the appropriate sub-models and the sensitivity of the simulation on the usage accurate and reliable boundary conditions. As a result, if the CFD model is not meticulously designed and the boundary conditions are not precisely defined, the results may not be accurate and reliable. One potential solution to overcome these accuracy issues is to integrate CFD and ODEs modeling using a manual or automated coupling approach (Shan et al., 2020; Zhai et al., 2022). Various coupling methodologies have already been applied and can be found in the literature. For example, Wang & Wong (2008), coupled CFD with the *ESP-r* building energy model for investigating

the ventilation system. The authors demonstrated that the results obtained using the coupling method were more accurate and reliable than those obtained using the standalone program. Yamamoto et al. (2018), used a coupling approach to analyze the thermal comfort conditions in a large office room with floor heating. The authors stated that the calculated temperature using the coupling approach closely matched the measured bulk temperature. In another study by Gowreesunker et al. (2013), CFD was coupled with Transient Systems (TRNSYS) software, where the calculated airflow from the CFD was implemented to TRNSYS for controlling the system.

A general observation emanating from the literature analysis is that more reliable and accurate results can be achieved when selected information from different building energy models is coupled with CFD models to improve initialization and boundary conditions in each snapshot (Shan et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2023; Zhai et al., 2005). In this work, the capability of high granularity modelling analysis using CFD approach (with coupled information from building energy models for increased accuracy) has also been incorporated in the simulation layer of the digital twin architecture as a complementary approach that can be used under offline analysis.

According to the literature analysis, there are different simulation approaches for modeling building operations, however, each approach has several advantages and limitations. Therefore, there is a need for an integrated approach capable of accurately emulating all the key aspects related to the operation of a building, either in real time for per-zone analysis or using offline analysis with increased granularity within each zone. Such an integrated approach should be used for HIL experiments to validate the effectiveness of new controllers and for the investigation of different *what-if* scenarios. Within this context, the aim of this work is the development of a digital twin architecture for smart buildings, considering the following requirements, features, and characteristics:

- Incorporation of an integrated modeling approach where the key aspects of a building are jointly modelled, including thermal comfort, indoor air-quality, electricity consumption, and users behavior.

- Development of a real-time building digital twin based on per-zone ODEs and macroscopic power balance modeling to enable real-time or faster-than-real-time execution. A faster-than-real-time digital twin can be used for investigating several *what-if* scenarios under extreme conditions, while a real-time digital twin can be utilized for HIL investigations when building controllers or building appliances are integrated in a non-invasive environment.
- Integration of CFD modeling in selected building zones for offline analysis to achieve increased granularity and spatiotemporal deviation information for zonal airflow and temperature. The CFD is integrated through a sequential coupling approach for high accuracy, where the results from the ODEs-based simulation at a selected snapshot, are used to set the boundary conditions (e.g., wall temperature, flow and HVAC temperature) of the CFD model.
- Development of a user-friendly software platform that can simultaneously interact with the *simulation layer* of the building (e.g., ODEs simulation for digital twins, and CFD simulation for offline analysis) and with the *physical layer* (e.g., actual device and sensors installed in the building). The interaction between both layers allows the use of field measurements for calibrating the accuracy of the simulation models. Furthermore, the software platform is used to configure the conditions and scenarios for the building digital twin, monitor the operation of the physical building and the digital twin, and integrate intelligent algorithms for managing and controlling the building.

The key contributions of this work are: (a) the design of an architecture for smart buildings digital twins that capture the important aspect related to the building's behavior, and the development of an associated software platform to enable the definition of parameters for each scenario, the interaction with both the physical and simulation layers of the building, and the integration of an energy management control scheme using real-time HIL configurations; and (b) the integration of CFD modeling within the above architecture using a proper coupling approach to increase the accuracy, enable high granularity, and provide increased spatiotemporal information about the airflow and temperature distribution within a building zone, which is used for offline analysis. The proposed architecture for smart buildings has been

utilized to demonstrate different use cases and to highlight the importance of such tools. A first use case investigates the impact of a temperature sensor fault on the thermal comfort of the occupants and the energy consumption of the building. The second use case demonstrates the operation of an energy management controller for battery storage systems to reduce electricity costs, considering a HIL interaction with the digital. Finally, the third use case investigates how the placement of sensors (thermostats) within a building zone can affect the overall thermal and economic operation of the building.

It is important to mention that this paper is an extension of the work published by Englezos et al. (2022), where the digital twin architecture was proposed. The current paper extends the previous work by incorporating CFD modelling in the overall architecture, in addition to ODEs modelling, to achieve increased spatiotemporal information and high granularity within a building zone. Furthermore, a sequential coupling methodology is introduced that integrates CFD analysis, resulting in high accuracy results. Additional use cases are included to highlight the impact of the sensor location within a building zone.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the proposed architecture for smart buildings digital twin and the associate software platform. Section 3 validates the accuracy of the simulation models based on both ODE and CFD modeling using field measurement from the physical layer. Section 4 presents the results of the aforementioned use cases. Section 5, provides conclusions and future work directions.

2 Building digital twin architecture

The concept for developing a building digital twin generally relies on four essential phases. As shown in Figure 1, the first phase is related to the collection of data and information regarding the geometry, materials, and equipment characteristics of the specific building of interest. This information is necessary for modelling the indoor environmental quality (IEQ) and energy consumption of the building using different model-based approaches. The second phase is related to the collection of live measurements from IAQ sensors and electricity meters installed in the building to monitor its real-time operating conditions. Additionally, live weather data are obtained either from weather stations or websites to be aware about the outdoor environmental conditions that affect the building operation. These live measurements are directly incorporated as inputs into simulation tools to accurately replicate the building operating conditions in real time. If there are unobservable states that are required as inputs in the digital twin, state estimation schemes can be incorporated to create pseudo measurements for these unmeasurable states. The simulation tools constitute the third phase of the building digital twin architecture, where model-based modelling is incorporated to simulate the IEQ and the energy consumption behavior of the building. Intelligent algorithms can also be employed to calibrate the building parameters in order to achieve an

Figure 1: General concept for developing a building digital twin based on four phases.

accurate response. In alternative concepts, data-driven modeling may be used instead of model-based simulations, to replicate the building's operation. The fourth phase is related to the development of a software platform to integrate the three previous phases. The software platform is responsible for the proper data exchange and the successful real-time execution of the simulation tools. Additionally, the software platform is used to integrate monitoring and control applications and to investigate different *what-if* scenarios.

The general concept described above is considered in designing a specific architecture for a building digital twin, as proposed in this work. The proposed architecture is presented in Figure 2 and consists of:

- (i) the *physical layer* that corresponds to the physical building and its components, including the building information (phase 1) and the sensors for live measurements (phase 2);
- (ii) the *simulation tools layer*

Figure 2: Proposed architecture of the smart building digital twin framework.

where the ODE, CFD and power balance modelling approaches (phase 3) have been integrated to emulate the building's operation; and (iii) the *software platform* (phase 4) that interacts with the simulation layer and the physical building for scenario definition, data aggregation, visualization, and intelligent management purposes. It is worth noting that ODE modeling is used to facilitate real-time or faster than real time zonal simulations of the building digital twin, while CFD modeling is complementarily used for high granularity offline simulations when the distribution of airflow and temperature within a zone is required.

2.1 Physical layer

The *physical layer* corresponds to the physical building and the field signals and measurements transmitted to the *software platform* and from the field devices installed in the physical building. Note that the physical building replicated in the *simulation layer* is the [SFC03 building](#), located in the campus of the University of Cyprus. As illustrated in Figure 2, SFC03 is a two-story building with gross area of 630 m², used for office and laboratory work. An 80 kW_p Photovoltaic (PV) system is installed in the surrounding area to partially cover the electrical demand of the building, while a battery storage system (15kW/15kWh) is also installed and used, among other purposes, to enhance the self-consumption capabilities of the building. The heating and cooling needs are satisfied through a central HVAC system. The users' behavior is incorporated into the simulation tools by considering stochastic arrivals, departures, and equipment utilization. Several sensors are installed to monitor the conditions in the building. IoT sensors are installed for monitoring the building's IEQ properties (i.e., temperature, humidity, CO₂, VOC, PMs) with high granularity. Sensor measurements can be retrieved in real-time through Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). Moreover, energy related measurements from smart meters, PV systems, power inverters and battery systems are retrieved over digital protocols to measure the overall electricity consumption and generation profile of the building in real time. The planimetries and electro-mechanical plans have also been used to design the 2- and 3-Dimensional (2D and 3D) representations of the building and provide the required information for the HVAC system, electrical loads, and building lights.

2.2 Simulation layer

In the *simulation layer* of the platform, two different simulation modeling approaches have been considered. The first approach relies on ODEs and power balance models to enable a common modeling approach for the air-quality and thermal behavior of each building zone and the power consumption of the entire building based on weather conditions and user habits. This approach is used to enable real-time or faster-than-real-time simulations of the building digital twin. The second approach relies on CFD modelling for offline simulation to analyze the airflow, air-quality and air-temperature distribution within a selected zone. This is a computational expensive simulation model that can only be used offline to enhance the granularity of collected spatiotemporal information. A sequential coupling approach is considered between the ODE and CFD simulations at each time step in order to increase the accuracy of the CFD model.

2.2.1 ODE simulation models for real-time digital twins

The first step for the creation of a building digital twin is related to the accurate design of the building's geometry to be used for the ODE modeling. In cases where there is a lack of an existing BIM model, as in Schweigkofler et al. (2022), the building geometry needs to be designed from scratch. This can be done using any related computer-aided design software. In this particular case, the existing 2D architecture floor level plans of the building were available in *AutoCAD*, and they were transformed into 3D using *Revit*. The final 3D geometry of the building under consideration is shown in Figure 3(a), while Figure 3(b) presents the 3D geometry of a selected room of the building that is used for validating both simulation models that have been incorporated within the digital twin, as presented in Section 3.

The next step for the implementation of the digital twin is the creation of the ODE and power balance simulation models. In this particular case, the *EnergyPlus* software is used as the ODE simulator (as shown in Figure 2), which is a building energy modeling engine of the USA Department of Energy designed for improving the energy footprint and assessing the performance of buildings (Jafar et al., 2020; EnergyPlus, 2017). This simulator takes as inputs the created geometry, the associated materials used in each surface, and weather data for the specific location. The *EnergyPlus* model is solved based on ODEs for each building zone considering the BIM, while the energy profile libraries for each power device are used for modeling the power balance at the building level. Power balance modeling at the building level includes the electrical behavior of appliances, the PV generation, and the operation of the battery storage system. Furthermore, the HVAC system of the building can be modeled in *EnergyPlus* using the technical documentation of the system and the electromechanical plans. As a result, *EnergyPlus* can be used for simultaneously simulating the indoor temperature, air quality, and electricity consumption and generation of the building. It should be highlighted that the accurate calibration of the model parameters can be achieved through an offline analysis where field measurements and state estimation schemes are used to fine tuning the unknown building parameters.

A weather data file (.epw) needs to be incorporated into the simulation model to emulate the outdoor environmental conditions of the simulation. It is noted that for simulating historical scenarios, the user can utilize existing weather data available for selected locations. However, for the development of the real-time building digital twin, the weather data are acquired from relevant websites that provide live or

Figure 3: (a) SFC03 building geometry and (b) geometry of the selected room used for validation

forecasted data (e.g., climate.onebuilding.org, weatherapi.com). The live or forecasted weather data are retrieved using APIs, and are processed into a weather data file format that is compatible with the *EnergyPlus* software (i.e., .epw). Moreover, certain stochastic profiles are also considered to emulate the user's behavior. If unmeasurable states are needed as an input to the simulation model for replicating the real-life conditions, then state estimation techniques can be utilized in an online processing approach to create pseudo-measurements for these unobservable states.

It should be clarified that the ODE models developed in *EnergyPlus* consider a 1-minute to 1-hour time resolution, allowing for real-time or faster-than-real-time execution as these models are computationally efficient. For example, in the case of the HIL investigation, it is critical to ensure the real-time execution of the model in order to facilitate the real-time digital twin concept. In this case, an external software needs to be developed to control the start or pause of the simulation, in order to meet the real-time execution requirements. Furthermore, for each solution step, the external software should be able to access the states/outputs of the simulation model and modify the inputs for the next step. In the proposed architecture, this functionality is provided by the software platform described in Section 2.3.

2.2.2 CFD modeling for high granularity offline analysis

In the *simulation layer* of the architecture, a CFD analysis tool is also incorporated to provide high granularity spatiotemporal information regarding the building operation within a zone. This is a demanding simulation tool and can only be used for offline simulation in cases where the airflow, air quality and air temperature space distribution within a zone needs to be analyzed.

In this work, the 3D CFD modelling approach is enabled by utilizing *Ansys Fluent* software (Fluent, 2020). The specific software allows for the preparation of the geometry, the meshing process and the setting up of the numerical model. The numerical model is based on the steady-state Reynolds-Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) equations using the Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure Linked Equations (SIMPLE) for pressure-velocity coupling. The standard k-epsilon (k- ϵ) model was used for turbulent flow simulations, while for viscous and convection terms the second order upwind scheme was used.

For the building analyzed in this work, the geometry used for CFD modeling is identical to the geometry of the selected room presented in Figure 3(b), while the mesh size of the geometry consists of approximately 4 million cells. The specific geometry includes 2 inlets and 3 outlets for ventilation, as well as 6 HVAC units that are used to circulate warm or cold air within the domain. The HVAC system is simulated as a simple mass flow inlet/pressure outlet system with uniform temperature and flow.

For increased accuracy of the CFD model, it is essential to properly set the boundary conditions. In this regard, a sequential coupling methodology is introduced here, involving the two simulation models and the physical layer, to accurately define the boundary conditions. At each snapshot where the CFD offline analysis needs to be performed, an ODE simulation is initially executed to calculate the room and wall temperatures at the specific time step. These temperatures are then utilized to appropriately set the boundary conditions of the CFD model. Additionally, ODE simulation results regarding the HVACs temperature and flow rate of each heating, cooling and fan modes are also implemented in the CFD to define the inlet airflow and temperature of each HVAC system. On the other hand, experimental measurements from the physical building (physical layer) have been obtained to set the boundary conditions related to the temperature and flow rate of each ventilation inlet. Furthermore, the presence of humans in specific locations of the building zone can be optionally considered.

2.3 Software platform

A *software platform* has been developed to integrate the proposed digital twin framework for smart buildings. The platform enables the interaction with both the *physical layer* and *simulation layer*, as well as facilitates data management, visualization, and the integration of intelligent algorithms, as shown in Figure 2. The development of the software platform relies on: (a) a local MATLAB backend software with a user interface that facilitates the interaction with the physical and simulation layers, allowing configuration of scenarios and control of the execution time of the simulations models; and (b) a cloud-based platform where *ThingSpeak* is used for data aggregation and proper APIs are employed to integrate web dashboards using *Grafana* and intelligent algorithms running in any server or in the cloud.

2.3.1 Local backend software

A local backend software is needed to interact with both the *physical* and *simulation layers* of the building and to manage data exchange and scenarios creation as shown in Figure 2. The backend software is developed in MATLAB and is responsible for managing the data exchange at the building level (e.g., measurements, set-points) between the local software and the simulated or physical building. Additionally, the backend is responsible for exchanging data with the cloud-based platform, either for storing the operating conditions in a cloud database or for receiving coordination signals that should be forwarded to the physical or simulated version of the building.

Another important aspect of the backend software is its responsibility for managing the time execution of the *simulation layer*, which is particularly important in the case of real-time digital twins. In such cases, especially when HIL configuration is needed, one minute of simulation time should correspond to one minute of actual time. To ensure the satisfaction of these simulation time execution constraints, the backend software uses proper timers to start and pause the execution of the ODE simulations. At each simulation step, the backend is responsible for exchanging data with the simulation model. For example, the zone temperature or the power consumption determined as an output by the simulation model should be obtained by the backend and either stored in a database or exchanged with other modules (e.g., local control schemes). Moreover, inputs that will be considered for the next simulation step, must also be provided by the backend (e.g., for changing the number of occupants in a building zone). On the other hand, in the case of the physical building, the backend must ensure the periodic sampling of measurements from the physical building and the periodic control of flexible devices.

The interaction between the backend and physical/simulation layer is achieved through the development of adequate middleware scripts. The IoT middleware is responsible for the interaction between the physical building and the software platform and is developed as a *MATLAB* script that ensures periodic communication with IoT sensors and intelligent appliances. This *MATLAB* script can receive IEQ measurements from the IoT sensors installed in the building using APIs. Energy consumption and

generation data from smart meters and PV inverters, are collected through the Modbus TCP communication protocol. Similarly, the same script is used to send coordination signals to the battery inverter (through *Modbus TCP*) to regulate the storage system operation. On the other hand, the communication between the software platform and the simulation layer is facilitated through the *EnergyPlus* middleware for the interaction with the ODE simulation models in case of real-time digital twins or faster than real-time scenarios investigations, while the *Ansys* middleware is used to interact with the CFD offline simulation models. The *EnergyPlus* middleware is used for the digital twins and is developed using the *EnergyPlus co-simulation toolbox* of *MATLAB*, allowing commands to initiate or pause an ODE simulation developed in *EnergyPlus*. Additionally, it enables the exchange of inputs/outputs between the backend software and the model at each control step. The *Ansys* middleware, on the other hand, allows the exchange of inputs/outputs with the CFD models, which can be used to set the boundary conditions and to collect the simulation results. Both *EnergyPlus* and *Ansys* middleware are utilized to facilitate the sequential coupling procedure required for an accurate CFD simulation. This procedure is performed in a semi-automated way. For the selected snapshots in which CFD analysis is required, the corresponding output results from the ODE simulations are first obtained by the backend software. Then the user can use this data and manually set the boundary conditions for the CFD. The user

interaction is needed to ensure that the minimization of risks of uncertainties and errors before starting the CFD simulation to ensure a more reliable and accurate CFD analysis.

An additional unit of this local software is related to the parametrization, scenarios creation, and visualization of the building's operation. Thus, a desktop application with a user interface is developed using the *MATLAB App Designer*, as presented in Figure 4. Through the user interface tool, users' behavior patterns, electricity consumption and generation profiles can be configured, based on either selected historical data or live inputs. Furthermore, the preferable comfort levels can be adjusted throughout the day, and specific disturbances or component failures can be emulated to create different potential conditions and scenarios. As a result, this tool can be used for the parametrization of the simulation models, and for creating several *what-if* scenarios to be investigated. Furthermore, this tool can also be utilized to monitor the operation of either the physical or the simulated building using higher data resolution. It should be noted that visualization tool is only accessible to local users with direct access to the local software. Finally, a controller unit is also included in this backend software, that allows local control or fault diagnosis schemes for device-level or building-level management to interact with the digital twin in every simulation step.

Figure 4: A screenshot of the user interface

2.3.2 Cloud-based platform

A cloud-based platform has also been developed that is able to interact with the local software backend for exchanging information, visualizing the building operation, integrating intelligent modules and enabling remote access for external users. Data collected by the local software platform from both the physical building (physical layer) or the digital twin (simulation layer) are uploaded and stored into a cloud-based IoT and data aggregation platform implemented in *ThingSpeak*. The exchange of data between the local software and the cloud-based platform is achieved using the standard IoT protocol MQTT, as shown in Figure 2. Therefore, all measurements related to the operation of the physical or simulated building are stored in the cloud allowing the creation of datasets that can be used for several research and innovation purposes.

The data aggregation platform (i.e., *ThingSpeak*) supports REST API calls (through HTTPs get requests commands), enabling a straightforward way to read measurements and write commands in its database. Through these API calls, a web-interface can be integrated for monitoring the operation of both the physical building and the digital twin, by connecting *ThingSpeak* with *Grafana*, which is an open-source multi-platform for analytics and interactive visualization. *Grafana* integration is achieved through the *Infinity Data Source* plugin. An example of the developed dashboard is demonstrated in Figure 5.

Moreover, the REST API calls can be utilized to integrate building-level smart modules in HIL configuration, enabling the intelligent management and optimization of simulated or actual operation of the building. These smart modules can be developed as software scripts that can be executed in any server,

Figure 5: Grafana dashboard example.

personal computer or cloud machine, while the interaction with the physical or simulated building is facilitated through *Thingspeak* considering API calls. This enables external users with the appropriate certification for access into these smart building facilities, to visualize or interact with the specific infrastructure.

3 Validation

After the upgrade of the building with the installation of sensors and IoT-enabled devices, the development of ODE and CFD simulation models, and the digital integration of the entire smart building framework through the development of the software platforms, then the calibration of the simulation models and validation of their accuracy are needed. The validation process presented in this section emphasizes on the thermal behavior of the building and is performed by comparing field measurements from the physical building with the results generated by the simulation layer, considering both ODE and CFD models.

3.1 Validation of ODE simulation models

The validation procedure for the ODE simulation model focuses mainly on the thermal conditions and it is achieved by conducting several on-site experiments. In this section, the experimental validation performed for the selected room shown in Figure 3(b) is presented. It is noted that a similar validation procedure has been performed for all the zone of the entire building. The developed ODE simulation in *EnergyPlus* uses a temporal model for the estimation of the thermal and IAQ behavior of each zone/room included in the building's digital twin. Therefore, the ODE model is generating a single state (i.e., temperature, humidity, etc.) for each building zone (e.g., room) at each simulation step.

Since it is observed that there is a non-negligible temperature difference inside the selected room, multiple IEQ sensors have been positioned to estimate the average room temperature. The temperature measurements were collected and processed using a weighted moving average approach in order to calculate a single temperature state per zone at each timestep. Four *Airthings Wave Plus* (i.e., sensors 1-4) and six *Aeon Multisensors* (i.e., sensors 5-10) have been installed in the room to measure the IEQ, as presented in Figure 6. The distribution of the sensors in the room has been arranged in a way that does not disrupt the occupants' use of the room.

An obstacle encountered during the validation of the building's digital twin was the lack of certain HVAC information (e.g., water temperature, fan air-inlet speed), which affects the model's response. In such cases, reverse engineering approaches or estimation schemes were applied to determine the missing

parameters based on experimental results. For instance, to determine the fan air-inlet speed of each of the six HVAC unit located in the specific room, airflow sensors have been utilized and experimental tests have been performed for different fan air-inlet speed levels, as regulated by the room's thermostat mode (e.g., 1, 2, 3 or auto). For example, by selecting level 3 on the thermostat, the maximum fan air-inlet speed for each HVAC system is measured by the sensors to be equal to 0.86 m/s. Therefore, the aggregated total maximum fan air-inlet speed for all HVAC units located in the specific room is determined as 5.16 m/s (based on the summation of the individual fan speed for each unit). Hence, the fan air-inlet speeds identified by the experimental measurements for each mode were incorporated into the ODE model of the building's digital twin created in *EnergyPlus*.

Figure 6: Position of IAQ sensors in the room. The Airthings sensors are noted with numbers 1-4,

and the Aeon sensors with numbers 5-10.

The validation phase for the thermal behavior of the ODE model of the digital twin is divided into two main experimental phases. The first phase focuses on validating the heat loss phenomena of the building's digital twin. The heat loss of a building is mainly affected by the building envelope and the insulation

materials. To capture this phenomenon, the temperature set-point should be reduced during winter (or increased during summer), or the HVAC system should be deactivated, and then the dynamic response of the building, related to the room temperature variation according to the heat loss characteristics, should be monitored. The second phase focuses on HVAC operating characteristics and the thermal energy transmission capabilities of the heating devices. During this phase, HVAC related parameters can be validated and re-calibrated. This phase is captured when the room temperature setpoint is increased during winter (or decreased during summer) and by monitoring the dynamic response of the room temperature in both the physical and the simulated building.

In the following subsections, two experimental studies are presented to validate the accuracy of the developed building digital twin based on the ODE model. In the first experiment, the air mass flow rate of the HVAC units was maintained at maximum (mode 3), while for the second experiment, it was automatically set (mode auto).

3.1.1 Validation experiment with constant fan coil speed

This experiment was performed on 25/01/2022, with the HVAC system operating from 08:00 onwards, and the windows of the room remained closed throughout the duration of the experiment. The weather conditions of the selected day are incorporated in the *EnergyPlus* model by using data obtained from weather sites, while the room occupancy (number of people in the room) was considered as a manual entry

Figure 7: Temperature of the validation room considering the physical building and the digital twin when a constant fan coil airflow is considered. (a) thermostat setpoint (yellow), temperature from the sensor in the physical building (grey), moving average temperature of the physical building (red), temperature of the building digital twin (blue); (b) total aggregated fan air-inlet flow rate for all six HVAC units.

to the model. Steady state temperature conditions were ensured before initiating the validation phase at 12:00 with a temperature set-point to be initially determined at 24°C. Then, the setpoint was adjusted to 26°C at 14:00, and to 22.5°C at 16:00. During this experiment, the fan coil air-inlet speed was set as constant to its maximum level (i.e., mode 3) by the room’s thermostat until 19:30 where the HVAC system is deactivated, as shown in Figure 7(b).

The temperature received by the four *Airthings Wave Plus* sensors and six *Aeon Multisensors* and the weighted moving average temperature calculated as a representative temperature for this zone (room) are presented in Figure 7(a), along with the temperature set-point and the temperature calculated by the building digital twin according to the *EnergyPlus* ODE model. Following the results presented in Figure 7, it can be observed that the calculated temperature by the digital twin (blue line) is very close to the actual temperature of the room (red line), which is calculated as the weighted moving average value from the ten temperature sensor values (grey lines).

3.1.2 Validation experiment with automatic fan coil speed

The second validation experiment was performed on 23/02/2022, focusing on the thermal behavior of the building when the fan coil speed was automatically determined by the thermostat (auto mode). In this case, the HVAC was activated at 08:00, with the temperature set-point adjusted to 24.4 °C. Then, at 12:00 and 17:15, the set-point was decreased to 23.5 °C and 22.8 °C respectively, while the HVAC units were deactivated at 20:00. The comparison among the setpoint temperature (yellow line), the IAQ sensors

Figure 8: Temperature of the validation room considering the physical building and the digital twin when an automatic fan coil airflow is considered. (a) thermostat setpoint (yellow), temperature from the sensor in the physical building (grey), moving average temperature of the physical building (red), temperature of the building digital twin (blue); (b) total aggregated fan air-inlet flow rate for all six HVAC units.

values (grey lines), the weighted average value representing the actual building temperature (red line), and the digital twin calculated temperature (blue line), is presented in Figure 8(a). Based on the comparison, it is demonstrated that the building’s digital twin is able to accurately capture the thermal response of the building when the fan coil speed is set to automatic, as shown in Figure 8(b).

3.2 Validation of CFD simulation models

For the validation of the CFD simulation model that has been developed for the high granularity analysis of the selected building zone, two different snapshots have been modelled. Both snapshots are based on the experiment performed on the 25th of January (as described in Section 3.1.1) where a constant fan flow rate for the HVAC units is considered. The first emphasizes on the steady state operating conditions at 15:00 (where the HVAC is activated), while the second snapshot focuses on the steady conditions at 21:00 (where the HVAC is deactivated). It is noted that to minimize the noise introduced into the CFD modeling and to reduce the complexity, for each snapshot the average conditions of a two-hours interval is considered, by taking the average of temperature and flow rate from one hour before to one hour after the selected timestep.

For setting the boundary conditions, the sequential coupling approach described in Section 2.2.2 is used. Thus, the ODE simulation model developed for the digital twin was executed first. The results provided by the simulation software (i.e., *Energyplus*) related to the wall temperatures of the specific zone and HVAC flow rate and temperature, are averaged for the two-hours intervals (e.g. time interval 14:00-16:00

Parameter	Inlet 1	Inlet 2	HVACs Each Unit	Wall 1	Wall 2	Wall 3	Wall 4
Snapshot at 15:00 (average value for the time interval 14:00 – 16:00)							
Average Temp. °C	24.2	24.2	25.6	26.2	26.1	26.1	25.4
Average Flow Velocity m/s	1.0	1.2	0.86	-	-	-	-
Snapshot at 21:00 (average value for the time interval 20:00 – 22:00)							
Average Temp. °C	21.0	21.0	-	21.8	21.5	21.6	20.8
Average Flow Velocity m/s	1.0	1.2	0.0	-	-	-	-

Table 1: Boundary Conditions for the CFD Simulations

for the snapshot of 15:00 and time interval of 20:00-22:00 for the snapshot of 21:00) and used as boundary conditions for the wall and HVAC units. Furthermore, the flow rates and temperatures for the two ventilation inlets have been taken from actual sensor measurements during the specific time-periods in order to set the ventilation boundary conditions. The average values used to configure the boundary conditions for the two snapshots under investigation are presented in Table 1.

For validating the CFD model considering the thermal behavior of the building zone, field measurements have been taken and analyzed from the 10 IAQ sensors installed in the selected zone. The sensors measurements have been post-processed by using a similar average calculation method of a two-hours interval explained in the previous paragraphs. For example, for validating the CDF results for the snapshot at 15:00, the average temperature of each sensor in the building zone is calculated for the time interval 14:00-16:00, while for the snapshot at 21:00 the average temperature is calculated considering the received measurements between 20:00 and 2200.

Then, the average temperature of each sensor is compared with the temperature calculated by the CFD analysis at the exact location of each sensor within the particular zone. The validation results are compared and presented in Figure 9. According to the comparison, it can be observed that the CFD analysis is able

Figure 9: Sensors average temperature and CFD results at each sensor location, for the snapshot at 15:00 (sensors: blue; CFD: orange) and for the snapshot at 21:00 (sensors: grey; CFD: yellow).

to accurately estimate the measured temperature in the actual building zone at each sensor location in both snapshots where the validation experiment was performed. For the snapshot at 15:00 an average error of 3.6% and a maximum error of 5.2% are observed, while for the 21:00 snapshot the average and maximum errors are equal to 3.6% and 5.4%, respectively for the 10 sensors under consideration. Hence, the developed CFD model is able to accurately analyze the temperature distribution within the building zone.

Moreover, the CFD model is also validated by comparing the average zone temperature (calculated by considering the temperatures at each sensor location), with the zone temperature calculated by the ODE simulation model developed for the building digital twin, and with the average value of the temperature measured from all the sensors installed in the physical building. The validation results are demonstrated in Figure 10 for the two snapshots at 15:00 and 21:00. According to the comparison it can be observed that both ODE and CFD modelling approaches are predicting remarkably well the physical building operating conditions measured by the sensors at both time snapshots. More specifically, at 15:00 the average temperature of the sensors is 25.5°C, while the zone temperature calculated by the ODE based digital twin is 25.7°C, and the average temperature calculated by the for the CFD is 25.4°C. Similarly, at

Figure 10: Comparison between the average room temperature obtained by the field temperature sensors (blue), the average CFD temperature calculated at the same location (orange), and the zone temperature calculated by the ODE simulation developed for the digital twin.

21:00 the average sensor temperature is 20.7°C, the zone temperature of the ODE model is 20.8°C and the average temperature by the CFD is 20.9 °C

Through this validation procedure, it becomes obvious that both the ODE and the CFD models developed, can accurately estimate the actual behavior of the building, and can be trusted for performing further investigations for different operating conditions.

4 Use cases demonstration

Since the accuracy of both ODE and CFD models has been validated in Section 3, the real-time and digital twin framework for smart building has been utilized for investigating different *what-if* scenarios and for demonstrating the building operation using a HIL approach. The CFD offline analysis has also been employed to investigate temperature distribution and optimal sensor placement within a building zone. In this section, selected use cases are presented to demonstrate how the proposed integrated framework for buildings can facilitate interesting investigations and can be used in research and innovation activities in the area of smart buildings.

4.1 Use case demonstration by using the real-time digital twin approach

The building digital twin developed by combining the ODE simulation model, field measurements and the software platform is used to demonstrate the following use cases: (a) *what-if* scenario considering a temperature sensor fault; (b) a real-time control HIL for building energy management when a battery system is integrated in the digital twin, and (c) a power HIL investigation where an actual battery system is managed according to the building digital twin operation.

4.1.1 Analysis of a *what-if* scenario considering a temperature sensor fault

The first use case investigates how a temperature sensor fault can affect the indoor air quality and energy consumption. An operational fault (e.g., offset fault) at the temperature sensor of the thermostat can lead to a poor energy performance and can create inconvenient environmental conditions for the occupants according to Papadopoulos et al., (2020). The specific *what-if* scenario aims on investigating the effect of such failures on the building operation in order to motivate the design of intelligent fault diagnosis and accommodation schemes to compensate the undesired impact of such sensor faults.

This use case focuses on an offset temperature sensor fault. In such failures, the temperature sensor of the thermostat used for controlling the air temperature of a specific zone provides a reading that contains a constant offset deviation from the actual room temperature. In the investigation results presented in Figure 11, such an offset fault is applied in the selected zone between 12:00 and 16:00 on 23/02/2022, where an

Figure 11: (a) Zone air temperature with health and faulty temperature sensor; and (b) Power consumption with healthy and faulty temperature sensor.

offset fault of $-2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is applied to the actual room temperature. Figure 11(a), compares the variation of the temperature inside the zone (room) by using both healthy and faulty sensors. First for the healthy sensor case, it can be observed that at 12:00, the temperature set-point (blue line) is changed from 24.5°C to 23.5°C , while the calculated temperature using the building's digital twin (black line) is able to track the set-point. After the decrease of the set-point, the HVAC system is almost deactivated to allow the temperature to decrease according to the heat loss of the building until the room reaches the new set-point. This results in a reduced power consumption by the HVAC system as indicated in Figure 11(b) (black line). For the faulty sensor, the same experiment has been repeated, but this time by applying an offset fault of $-2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to the actual room temperature between 12:00 and 16:00. The calculated room temperature using the building's digital twin with the faulty sensor is presented with red color in Figure 11(a). As it can be observed, the error in the temperature sensor affects the HVAC system operation and as a result the room temperature is increased causing violation of the thermal comfort for the occupants. At the same time, as shown in Figure 11(b), the HVAC system absorbs more active power which leads to a higher energy consumption (26.05kWh total energy consumption compared to 17.15kWh of the base scenario). Summarizing the findings from the comparison between the healthy and the faulty temperature sensors, it can be observed that such a sensor fault can impact negatively both the air quality comfort level and the energy consumption of a building. Therefore, algorithms capable of timely detecting and accommodating such faults in buildings can lead to significant savings while ensuring the occupants' comfort level.

Figure 12: Electricity demand, PV generation and power exchange with the grid without a battery.

4.1.2 Energy management demonstration with and without battery system (Control-HIL)

The capability of the proposed building digital twin to properly capture the thermal, air quality and electrical operation of the building at the same time enables its utilization for energy management investigations. The energy consumption of the HVAC system, in order to maintain the desired air quality and thermal comfort for occupants, in combination with the lighting and electrical appliances consumption determined according to the utilization by the occupants, define the total energy demand of the building. On the other hand, an 80 kWp PV installation with south orientation and a tilt angle of 33° is considered to partially cover building's energy demand.

In Figure 12, the building's electricity demand (red line) on 25/01/2022 is demonstrated. An increased consumption is observed between 09:00 until 19:00 where the HVAC systems, lights and appliances of the building are utilized. The PV generation (green line) is also presented in the same figure for the particular semi-cloudy day, with a peak generation of 50 kW. The power exchange with the grid (yellow line) is also demonstrated, indicating that the building imports power (positive value) to cover its energy demand, besides the time window between 07:45 and 13:30 where the excess PV power creates reverse power flow and the building exports power (negative) to the grid. For the particular day, the building imports 189 kWh and exports 74 kWh.

In cases where a behind-the-meter battery storage system is available, a flexible energy management can be achieved to increase the self-consumption and reduce the electricity cost. When the building is operating under a net-billing scheme, the export energy is sold at a significantly lower price compared to

(a)

(b)

Figure 13: (a) Electricity demand, PV generation and power exchange with the grid, and battery operation (battery emulated within the digital twin) and (b) Battery SOC (when battery is emulated within the digital twin).

the purchased price for the import energy. In this context, a battery system can be utilized to increase the self-consumption capability of the building, reducing the amount of energy exported at lower prices and therefore, reduce the total electricity cost. In self-consumption mode (Chakraborty et al., 2018), the battery uses the export power to charge, given that the battery inverter ratings are not violated, and that the battery is not fully charged. Then, the battery discharges to meet the energy demand when the building imports energy, until the battery is fully discharged.

The energy related operation of the building by considering the usage of a battery system for flexible energy management is demonstrated in Figure 13. For this investigation a battery system with 60 kWh usable capacity is considered, with the minimum and maximum State Of Charge (SOC) set at 30% and 90% respectively. As it can be observed from Figure 13 (a), despite the fact that the energy demand and PV generation are the same with the case demonstrated in Figure 12, the battery system operates in self-consumption mode (blue line) and therefore, is changing the power exchange between the building and the grid (yellow line). It is also important to be noted that the controller for the self-consumption mode is developed as a smart module in the cloud-based platform of Figure 2, by considering a control HIL configuration, where the controller is able to receive measurements for the building digital twin operation and manage the battery operation integrated within the digital twin.

Furthermore, according to Figure 13 (b), the battery SOC is initially at 80% and the battery is covering the building energy demand until it reaches the minimum SOC at 03:45. Then, the building is importing energy to cover the demand until 07:45, where the PV generation creates excess power. From 07:45 until 11:00, the excess power is used to charge the battery (until the maximum SOC is reached). The remaining excess power (11:00-13:30) is exported. Afterwards, at 13:30 the energy demand exceeds the PV generation and thus, the battery begins discharging to meet the excess demand until it is fully discharged at 17:15. For the rest of the day, the building imports energy to cover its demand.

In this use case, with the battery system operates in self-consumption mode, it is observed that the total import energy is reduced to 97 kWh (compared to 189 kWh without the battery) and the export energy is reduced to 22 kWh (compared to 74 kWh without the battery). The utilization of the battery in the energy management of the building reduces the total electricity cost to 31 euros, compared to 55 euros for the case without the battery (assuming a simplified cost calculation with 36 and 18 cent per kWh for import and export energy respectively). In addition, by employing more sophisticated algorithms (Tziouvani et al., 2021), the building electricity cost can be further reduced when a variable pricing scheme is applied.

4.1.3 Power-HIL investigation by controlling an actual battery

The same use case with the previous subsection is repeated in this section, but in this case, an actual battery system is connected in a power-HIL configuration with the building digital twin. An actual LG Chem RESU 10H is installed in the physical building, emulated by the digital twin, and is integrated through a Fronius Symo Hybrid 5 kW inverter. The actual battery is managed by a self-consumption algorithm running as a smart module (as shown in Figure 2) in control-HIL approach, based on the electricity consumption measured by the building real-time digital twin. Thus, the actual battery, the building digital twin and the self-consumption algorithm are connected in a combined control and power HIL configuration. To ensure the sizing compatibility, a scaling factor of 10 is applied to both the inverter ratings and the battery capacity, enabling the actual battery to emulate an equivalent battery with 50 kW and 60 kWh (the same configuration with the previous subsection).

(a)

(b)

Figure 14: (a) Electricity demand, PV generation and power exchange with the grid, and the actual battery operation (actual battery and digital twin connected as HIL); and (b) Actual battery state of charge (when connected as HIL).

Figure 14 demonstrates the building energy operation with the battery connected in a power HIL configuration. It can be observed that an almost identical operation is achieved compared to results of the previous subsection. The only deviations are due to the actual standby losses of the battery which have not been considered in the battery modeling of the previous subsection. This results in three additional charging instances when the SOC is reduced during noon. Additionally, the standby losses cause the battery to fall below its minimum SOC (30%) during the night. The HIL experiment highlights important information that can be used to improve the operation of the actual battery system before the operation mode is applied in the actual device or building.

4.2 Use case demonstration for the temperature deviation by using the CFD analysis

The integration of CFD modeling in the proposed architecture for investigating the operation of smart buildings enables the capability to use this offline analysis tool for studying the airflow and air temperature distribution within a building zone. In the particular use cases demonstrated in this section, the CFD tool is utilized to analyze the air temperature distribution inside the room and to identify the optimal sensor placement that properly represents the average room temperature, when the HVAC is activated and when it is deactivated.

Both use cases focus on investigating the temperature distribution within a selected building zone (room presented in Figure 3(b)). The two snapshots that were analyzed during the validation process for the CFD

Figure 15 Architectural drawing of the floor plan of the selected room indicating the cross-section planes that are demonstrated by the CFD analysis (green lines A-A', B-B', C-C', D-D', E-E', F-F').

model, see Section 3.2, have also been used for the demonstration of this use case. Thus, the boundary conditions are already provided in Table 1, for the snapshot at 15:00 (where the HVAC is activated) and for the snapshot at 21:00 (where the HVAC is deactivated).

For investigating the temperature distribution within the selected building zone, seven different temperature cross-section planes have been extracted from the CFD tool for both use cases. Six of these planes are vertical cross-section planes that highlight the positions of the 10 sensors and their surrounding thermal environment. Moreover, these six planes have been selected since they are highly affected by the ventilation inlet, the HVAC units and the wall temperatures. The seventh plane is a horizontal cross-section plane of the floor plan at height 165 cm. The vertical cross-sections demonstrated in this analysis are indicated in the floor plan presented in Figure 15.,Furthermore, by analysing the temperature distribution around the specific sensors, a reliable and clear image of the thermal environment can be extracted, that can be beneficial for the identification of the optimal location for the thermostat sensor when the HVAC is activated and to specify a representative location of the temperature sensor when the HVAC is deactivated.

4.2.1 Temperature distribution and sensor placement when HVAC is activated

The first use case considers a snapshot of the building operating conditions of the specific room at 15:00 (on 25/01/2022), when the HVAC is activated and the thermostat is set to 26°C. The CFD analysis results are demonstrated in Figure 16 (a)-(f), where the temperature distribution (temperature contours) in the vertical cross-section planes A-A' (related to sensor 1), B-B' (related to sensor 2), C-C' (related to sensor 4), D-D' (related to sensor 5), E-E' (related to sensor 6) and F-F' (related to sensors 3, 7-10), are presented, respectively. Moreover, in Figure 16 (g), the temperature contour of the room using the horizontal cross-section plane at the height of the seated people is presented. Through the analysis of the temperature distribution in the seven planes, it can be observed that the temperature does not follow a uniform distribution pattern, but it is highly influenced by the temperature of the ventilation and HVAC airflow, as well as the temperature of the walls. Therefore, depending on the position of the plane, relative to the

Figure 16: CFD analysis results when HVAC is activated (at 15:00). The temperature contours presented in the vertical cross-section planes (a) A-A' (sensor 1); (b) B-B' (sensor 2); (c) C-C' (sensor 4); (d) D-D' (sensor 5); (e) E-E' (sensor 6); (f) F-F' (sensors 3,7-10); and (g) in the horizontal cross-section plane at the height of people.

HVAC, ventilation inlet, and to the walls, the temperature exhibits different patterns, while a total deviation of 2°C is observed within the building zone during the specific snapshot.

Regarding the optimal sensor location study, since the temperature distribution inside the room is affected by different factors such as the ventilation inlets, the temperature of the walls, the breathing of the seated occupants and etc., different technical requirements and restrictions should be considered before deciding the optimal sensor location. In general, the following technical requirements, same for both CFD use cases, are considered for determining the sensor location:

- the sensor should be placed in an area where the temperature closely represents the mean room temperature,
- the sensor should not be placed in areas near the seated occupants or to the ventilation inlets,
- the sensor should not be placed near the windows or near the door of the room.

Taking into consideration, the technical requirements and using the results presented in Figure 16, it can be observed that the sensors should be avoided to be placed on the walls that are having high temperature (close to the max temperature) such as the walls shown in Figure 16 (a), Figure 16 (b) and Figure 16 (f). Furthermore, as shown in Figure 16 (d), low temperature inlet flow from the ventilation is creating low temperature regions that are not representative of the room average temperature and may create deviations that in turn may accelerate the operation of the HVAC units. By accelerating the operation of the HVAC units using wrong temperature measurements, may lead to higher energy consumption, and at the same time, violation of the occupants' comfort. The locations presented in Figure 16 (c) and Figure 16 (e), appear to be the most promising for optimal sensors placement. However, the location presented in Figure 16 (e), is very close to the seated occupants and therefore should be avoided. Finally, the location presented in Figure 16 (c), satisfies all the technical requirements, while the temperature distribution closely aligns with the mean temperature of the room. Therefore, it was chosen for the sensor placement. The optimal sensor location is presented with bright red color dot in Figure 16 (c) and Figure 16 (g).

4.2.2 Temperature distribution when HVAC is deactivated

The second use case considers a snapshot of the specific room at 21:00 (on 25/01/2022) when the HVAC is deactivated. The results (temperature contours) from the CFD analysis are presented in Figure 17 (a)-(g) for the same six horizontal and the one vertical planes, as mentioned in the previous use case.

According to the results, it can be observed that despite the HVAC systems is deactivated, the temperature is not uniformly distributed within the building zone, but warmer and colder areas have appeared, similar to the previous case. However, in this case the temperature distribution in the room is mainly affected by the ventilation inlet and the walls temperatures, resulting in colder temperature on the left side of the room, as indicated by the temperature contour in the horizontal plane presented in Figure 17 (g). It is also noted that due to the deactivation of the HVAC units in this use case, the total temperature deviation is 1°C, instead of 2°C that has been observed in the previous case where the HVAC was activated.

Figure 17: CFD analysis results when HVAC is deactivated (at 21:00). The temperature contours presented in the vertical cross-section planes (a) A-A' (sensor 1); (b) B-B' (sensor 2); (c) C-C' (sensor 4); (d) D-D' (sensor 5); (e) E-E' (sensor 6); (f) F-F' (sensors 3,7-10); and (g) in the horizontal cross-section plane at the height of people.

Regarding the analysis for the optimal sensor location, using the same technical constraints described in the previous use case, it can be observed that the temperature is very high (close to the max temperature) in planes A-A' in Figure 17 (a), B-B' in Figure 17 (b) and C-C' in Figure 17 (f). Therefore, these specific planes should not be used for sensor placement. On the other hand, Planes D-D' in Figure 17 (d) and E-E' in Figure 17 (e), are close to the breathing seated occupants and ventilation inlets and therefore are also inappropriate choices for the optimal sensor location. Finally, a possible solution is by placing the sensor on the wall described by the plane C-C' in Figure 17 (c). The possible optimal sensor location is presented with bright red color dot at Figure 17 (c) and Figure 17 (g). Similar to the first use case, the temperature at the specific wall is close to the mean temperature of the room without any cold or hot temperature regions and satisfies all of the technical constraints set.

Summarizing the findings from the CFD modelling in both conditions, it can be concluded that the temperature is not distributed uniformly and that is strongly influenced by different factors such as the airflow and temperature from the ventilation inlets and HVAC system, and the walls temperature. Therefore, for the optimal sensor placement the different technical constraints, that have been set in the previous paragraphs, should be satisfied before placing the sensors. For example, in both use cases, the optimal locations for the sensors have been decided based on the temperature distribution on the specific wall, the proximity to the average temperature of the room, the impact of the different parameters such as the airflow from the ventilation inlet and HVAC, and the walls temperature.

Placing the sensors in optimal locations is very important as it affects the operation of the HVAC, the thermal comfort of the occupants and the energy consumption. For example, when a sensor is placed at the optimal location and provides a representative room temperature, the HVAC system operates smoothly to ensure the minimum temperature deviation in the room in relation to the user set-point. However, when inaccurate measurements (non-representative of the average room temperature) are provided from the thermostat, the HVAC may accelerate or reduce rapidly its operation, impacting the thermal comfort of the occupants and the energy consumption. On the other hand, when the HVAC is turned off and non-

representative measurements of the temperature are provided, may have as a result the HVAC unit to delay or accelerate its reactivation, again having a significant impact on the thermal comfort level and energy consumption.

5 Architecture Capabilities – Discussion

For further analysis of the capabilities and functionalities of the proposed digital twin architecture, recently developed BIM and digital twins' architectures from the literature have been compared with the proposed digital twin architecture.

Eneyew et al. (2022), proposed a multi-layer digital twin architecture and a framework for smart buildings digital twins focusing on the integration of BIM and IoT data sources. The authors showed that the proposed architecture and framework enable the semantic interoperability between the different layers of the digital twin and satisfy the real-time data requirements. However, despite the implementation of an application layer that can be used for real time monitoring, visualization and thermal comfort assessment using historical or live sensor data; a software layer that can integrate smart algorithms (e.g., energy management schemes, fault diagnosis analysis, etc.) for the decision support system has not been implemented. In contrast, the digital twin architecture that has been proposed and developed in this work, includes an API framework that allows the straight-forward integration of control schemes and smart modules to automate the building operation. Additionally, the architecture developed during this study includes a simulation layer capable of emulating different operating scenarios under normal or extreme conditions, and not only to reproduce live or historical data obtained from the sensors. Therefore, the digital twin developed in this work can be used to investigate different *what-if* scenarios and to test solutions in a non-invasive manner under extreme conditions.

Moreover, Arsiwala et al. (2023), developed a digital twin architecture by integrating BIM, IoT and artificial intelligence algorithms in order to visualize indoor air quality of a small-scale building for automating, monitoring and controlling the equivalent CO₂ emissions. The authors demonstrated that the proposed architecture can be used successfully for the prediction of future emissions based on the received data, while it includes an alerting system that provides information for various critical parameters. However, this architecture primarily focuses only on indoor air quality parameters, while the energy perspective is not analysed. Similar to the architecture proposed by Arsiwala et al. (2023), Valinejadshoubi

et al. (2021) developed an IoT and BIM based architecture that includes an automated alert system but focuses only on the monitoring and analysis of thermal comfort, excluding from the investigation the energy consumption aspects that are highly coupled with the thermal operation of the building. The non-consideration of the coupled phenomena between the electricity and the indoor air-quality of the building in the two aforementioned architectures, limits their capabilities to be used for different kind of investigations. On the other hand, the digital twin architecture proposed in this work, incorporates both the analysis of important indoor air quality parameters, such as temperature, flow rates, CO₂, and humidity, as well as building energy modelling (e.g., energy consumption of heating/cooling systems, energy generation by renewable resources). This integration of indoor air quality and building's energy enables interesting studies considering the coupling aspects between the two main building domains.

Furthermore, in order to investigate even further the capability level of the proposed digital twin architecture, the five-level ladder taxonomy scale, proposed by Menasa (2021), was used. Based on the specific taxonomy scale, there are five different levels of BIM and digital twins' architectures:

1. Level 1 is the lowest level and includes BIMs that are used for conceptual designs and construction scheduling,
2. Level 2 includes integrated BIM and simulation platforms that can be used for estimation and simulation-based predictions,
3. Level 3 incorporates platforms that include sensors and can be used for real time visualization and real time monitoring purposes,
4. Level 4 includes the platforms that may include artificial intelligent algorithms and can be used for decision making and data prediction,
5. Level 5 is the highest level and includes holistic platforms that can analyse indoor air quality, thermal comfort and energy consumption and can be used for control, prediction and optimization purposes. The holistic platforms incorporate both simulation software and sensors.

Based on the scaling method, the proposed architecture can be ranked at Level 5. This is due to the fact that the building energy modelling approach (ODEs based model) allows real-time and/or faster than real-time simulations able to capture the building behavior by considering the thermal, air-quality, and electricity building domains, while incorporating the user habits. Moreover, the CFD modelling approach can be used for even more detail analysis of the distribution of important indoor air quality and thermal comfort parameters within a building zone. In addition, the development of the software platform associated with the proposed architecture enables the interaction with both the actual and the simulated building, as well as the integration of different control, optimization, and diagnosis algorithms to manage the operation of the building under different scenarios.

6 Conclusions

This paper proposed an architecture for investigating the operation of smart buildings, where a new software platform has been developed to integrate the physical layer of the building and the simulation layer. Within the simulation layer, a real-time or faster than real-time simulation model, based on ODE and power balance approach, has been incorporated to facilitate the development of the building digital twin that is capable of capturing the building's behavior, considering the thermal, air-quality, and electricity domains while incorporating the user habits. Additionally, a CFD simulation model is also integrated to enable offline analysis with higher granularity within the building zones. An integrated software platform has been developed that can communicate with both the physical and the simulation layer of the building, allowing the visualization of the building operation, the calibration of the simulation models, and the intelligent management of the building operations.

The models for the building digital twin based on ODE and for the offline CFD analysis have been validated using field measurements at two different time instances and scenarios. From the validation procedure, it can be observed that both models are predicting accurately the sensors temperature with a maximum error less than 1% in both ODE and CFD approaches. Therefore, the models can be trusted in order to be utilized for further investigations and analysis.

The proposed framework for smart building is also utilized to demonstrate how a temperature sensor fault can affect the occupants' thermal comfort and the energy consumption of the heating system. Furthermore, the real-time digital twin is used to investigate the performance of energy management algorithms for smart buildings using hardware in the loop configuration. In addition, the CFD analysis tool is used to investigate the temperature distribution within a building zone and to demonstrate how to select a proper location for the temperature sensors. Hence, the proposed architecture for smart buildings' investigations enables a framework that can be used for performing different studies, and for testing and demonstrating new monitoring and control algorithms for buildings.

As concluding remarks, it can be said that the proposed digital twin architecture is a promising tool that can be executed in real time or even faster than real time, allowing the analysis of not only energy consumption but also indoor environmental quality, and can be used successfully for the investigation of different *what-if* scenarios and fault diagnostics studies. Additionally, the usage of the proposed digital twin architecture can be beneficial for operators/managers of buildings, as it enables fast and accurate detection of hazardous and dangerous events, such as air contamination. Moreover, storing and reporting real time data, or even testing different fault diagnostics scenarios can be very useful for the decision-makers to improve the policies and protocols related to health and safety of occupants in buildings. Furthermore, the proposed architecture enables the examination of the building's energy consumption based on the operational modes of the different energy harvesting appliances (e.g., heating/cooling devices), the number of people in the building, and the behavior of the occupants. This allows the identification of possible holistic management strategies to reduce the overall energy consumption with significant environmental sustainability and economic benefits.

Future work will focus on addressing the weaknesses of the current building's digital twin architecture. In particular, the capability of widely applying and testing the architecture in larger-scale buildings is a key priority. Thus, it is important that the proposed architecture will be modularized and standardized to allow a straight-forward incorporation of new large-scale buildings with a minimum overhead. Towards this direction, the modeling procedure should be automated, different types of cooling/heating systems and appliances should be modelled, and the association between the sensors and the modeling results should be performed in an interoperable manner enhancing the flexibility, accuracy, and reproducibility of the proposed architecture.

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